

IMPORTANCE OF SOCIOLINGUISTICS IN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

Muradova Zuxra Shuxratovna

11 –specialized public school

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928108>

Abstract: This research paper is very significant for language teachers because learners may have different personalities, social lives, and ethnicities. Instructors should pay attention to the group of learners and their needs. Educators take into account their family habits, social status, and language levels. Because of their background knowledge and learning habits, they acquire the new skills easily, and their knowledge is better than that of the second group. Social life and the people around us can influence language use and learning context.

Key words: Sociolinguistics, learning context, ethnicity, social life, background knowledge.

Learners can be divided into two different subgroups according to their social factors, language background, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status. It is clear that social factors such as age, gender, and social class can have an impact on second and foreign language acquisition. **First-group** students originally come from a rich family, whose parents have well-paid jobs. They know the English language very well because they attended the extra-curricular classes from an early age. Ethnicity and social class are related to the economic status in a society and every person belongs to the ethnic group in this world. These learners belong to the upper class in a society whose family is rich. Wardhaugh and Fuller (2014) noted that sociolinguistics is about our daily life and social class, ethnicity involve the role of language in education. . Ethnicity has effected language variety such as people may have different ethnic groups. Some learners come from rural areas and some of them urban. They often use “borrowed” variety and accent that their speech can be various by borrowed language (Fought, 2011, p.242). To sum up, their ethnic identity can be built from outside communities.

The learning context is the classrooms of the school, which are decorated with colorful posters and pictures. There are several English classrooms in the school that are very modern and well-equipped. Learners are able to use computers and projectors when they have to watch videos according to the theme. There are whiteboards and different pictures on the wall that attract students’ attention. In listening activities, they can use headphones and speakers. The classroom is always peaceful and convenient for learning new knowledge. The most important factor is that gender, age, ethnicity and race should be taken into consideration in learning context. The reason for this is that learners feel very comfortable in the class and they may not have any conflicts during the lesson. School syllabus also should be appropriate for every nation and country. As there are different gender, age, ethnic groups and races in the world. Their cultures, customs, and traditions can be varied, and they should be able to get knowledge according to this. It is the main aspect of the language learning process, and this sociolinguistic study is very significant. Booven (2018) stated that language learning and teaching will be enhanced by sociolinguistic competence (SC) and interactional competence (IC). Sociolinguistic competence is based on using appropriate language that is understandable in context. When teaching English as a second language, teachers should know learners’ abilities and social norms.

Sociolinguistic competence is based on using appropriate language in the context of learning. Language instructors have to take these aspects into consideration that play an important role in the learning process. Gender, sexuality, and ethnicity are also included in this paper, which is the main part of sociolinguistics.

References:

1. Baugh, J. (2005). Linguistic profiling. In S. Makoni, G. Smitherman, A. F. Ball, & A. K. Spears (Eds.). *Black linguistics: language, society, and politics in Africa and the Americas* (pp. 155-168).
2. Booven, C. D. (2018). Developing sociolinguistic and interactional competence. *The TESOL Encyclopedia of English Language Teaching*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0286>
3. Chalipa, S. (2013). The Effect of Inductive Vs. Deductive Instructional Approach in Grammar Learning of ESL Learners. *DIJARS/2013/June/vol/Issue/1369*.
4. Deumert, A. (2011). Multilingualism. In R. Mesthrie (Ed.), *The Cambridge handbook of sociolinguistics* (pp.262-282). *Cambridge University Press*.